

Evidence of Learning: A Glance on Performance-Based Assessment in Distance Learning of Technology and Livelihood Education

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Abstract:- The primary goal of this study is to explore performance-based assessment in distance learning of Technology and Livelihood Education. The study employed a phenomenological research design which aims to determine the experiences and perceptions of the seven (7) teacher participants. Three themes emerged on the experiences of TLE teachers as they conduct performance-based assessment in distance learning. These are acquiring assessment knowledge and skills on distance learning, involving students in the making, and extending time for at-risks students. Meanwhile, three themes also emerged on the coping mechanisms of TLE teachers to the challenges in conducting performance-based assessment in distance learning, three themes also emerged. The themes are adjusting to students' socioeconomic status, employing different methods in monitoring the quality of students' work, and scheduling time for assessment design and feedback. Furthermore, three themes were also noted in the education management insights drawn from the experiences of teachers. These are lifelong learning and being open to change, escalating students' engagement and being sensitive and responsive. The results implied that TLE teachers conduct performance-based assessments in a student-centered approach. Varied methodologies were applied by them to reach out both online and offline students. The results generated provided comprehensive data in conducting future research with similar or relevant scope.

Keywords:- Performance-Based Assessment, Technology and Livelihood Education, Experiences, Challenges, Insights, Davao City.

I. INTRODUCTION

➤ *The Problem and its Setting*

Assessment is an essential element of instruction for Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) teachers, as it enables them to evaluate the extent of effective learning. Traditional assessments, particularly multiple-choice tests, are frequently perceived as accessible methods for instructors of English as a second language (Rukad, 2010). Teachers are able to objectively evaluate students' learning outcomes without the interference of personal biases as a result of these tests. Multiple-choice testing, as noted by Abedi (2010), has been found to have limitations in that it does not offer a comprehensive assessment of students' knowledge and skills

in content areas. Additionally, conventional evaluations frequently neglect to assess the necessary competencies and higher-order thinking skills that are essential for success in both the classroom and the workplace (Pierce & O'Malley, 1992).

A more authentic alternative is being implemented by TLE instructors in light of these limitations, as evidenced by the increasing prevalence of performance-based assessments. Magone and Glaser (2002) conducted research that indicates performance-based assessments enable students, particularly those with diverse language backgrounds, to participate in intricate cognitive activities, including strategy generation, task monitoring, information analysis, and the application of reasoning skills.. Performance-based assessments have been incorporated into the curricula of numerous countries. The incorporation of performance assessments in national examinations is supported by notable educational policy frameworks, such as the National Education Goals Panel (2000) and the National Council on Education Standards and Testing (2002). For example, the SAT has included a brief essay as a standard performance evaluation since the spring of 2005, and the ACT has also implemented a writing test option (Herrick, 1999).

Curriculum 2013 in Indonesia prioritizes performance-based assessment as an adjunctive grading system to conventional assessments. In Home Economics courses, performance-based assessments are of particular importance. Prastikawati (2018) found that students responded favorably to performance-based assessments, with nearly all of the 30 students surveyed indicating that this method enhanced their comprehension of the skills being taught, in contrast to conventional assessment methods. Additionally, 24 of the 30 students expressed that traditional assessments were inadequate for demonstrating the skills they acquired in Home Economics.

Japan has attracted international attention for its industrial and technology education practices, particularly its increased implementation of performance-based assessments within the curriculum (Tanaka, 2010). In contrast to selected response assessments, which are limited to inferences, performance assessments directly evaluate students' capacity to implement their knowledge in real-world scenarios. When utilized in a formative manner during the learning process, these assessments are essential learning instruments that provide students and parents with valuable feedback through

the use of rating scales or rubrics. Students' comprehension, motivation, and accomplishments are improved through their participation in the development of criteria and rubrics, as well as self-assessment (Tanaka, 2010).

The current curriculum in the Philippines is designed to meet the needs of 21st-century learners, with a particular emphasis on student performance. TLE instructors prioritize the acquisition of essential skills for the future by furnishing learners with information regarding tools, materials, and the steps to follow for a variety of assignments. Performance assessments are essential for students in TLE subjects such as electrical installation maintenance, cookery, and computer hardware servicing, notably under the K to 12 Curriculum Program, as they assist students in refining their abilities.

Performance-based assessments are not without their drawbacks, despite their numerous benefits. Performance tasks are restricted to specific skills that are pertinent to the task at hand, in contrast to selected response tests, which can evaluate a wide range of abilities (Borrich, 2005). It is imperative to exercise caution when extrapolating a student's capabilities beyond the immediate learning objectives. Furthermore, performance assessments typically necessitate more time than selective response instruments; nevertheless, they can be seamlessly integrated into the standard instructional process (Metin, 2008). Nevertheless, the current context of distance learning presents TLE instructors with challenges in conducting performance-based assessments, such as addressing issues related to instructional quality, hidden costs, technology misuse, and student attitudes toward the new learning platform (Arda, 2020).

➤ *Research Questions*

- What are the experiences of TLE teachers as they conduct performance-based assessments in distance learning?
- How do TLE teachers cope with the challenges in conducting performance-based assessments in distance learning?

- What educational management insights are drawn from the findings of the study?

➤ *Theoretical Lens*

David Kolb's (1984) Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) builds on John Dewey's emphasis on connecting education with students' lived experiences. ELT provides a framework for understanding the experiential learning process, highlighting the relationship between curriculum mastery and experiential engagement. It outlines a cyclical model with four components: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation. This model emphasizes authentic learning by tying lessons to real-life applications, fostering social skills, and supporting performance-based assessments such as portfolios, reflective journals, and presentations (Gama & Fernández, 2009; Hancock, 2003). While experiential learning outcomes vary between individuals, its transformative potential aligns with Darling-Hammond's (2000) and Wilhoit & Pittenger's (2014) emphasis on skills development for life applications.

Contemporary Cognitive Learning Theory has expanded understanding of the complexity of learning and the diverse means needed to assess it effectively. Unlike earlier behaviorist approaches, this theory posits that learning involves inference, judgment, and active mental construction (Resnick, 1987; Shepard, 2000). New findings reveal that intellectual abilities develop socially and culturally, and prior knowledge significantly shapes new learning. Key aspects include metacognition, deep understanding for knowledge transfer, and the importance of motivation and personal identity in learning (Perkins, 1992; Perkins & Blythe, 1994). Performance assessments, which focus on how students organize and apply knowledge to solve complex problems, align closely with contemporary cognitive learning principles (Khattri, Reeve, & Kane, 1998). These assessments emphasize meaningful learning through reflection, construction, and contextual application over rote memorization.

Fig 1 The Conceptual Framework of the Study

The conceptual framework of the study is presented in figure 1. Based on the figure, there are two interconnected variables. These variables are the (1) Experiences of TLE teachers in conducting performance-based assessment in distance learning; (2) TLE teachers coping mechanisms based on the limitations in conducting performance-based assessment in distance learning; and (3) Insights drawn from the experiences of TLE teachers.

II. METHOD

➤ *Design and Procedure*

This study employs a qualitative approach, specifically a phenomenological research design, to explore and assess teachers' experiences and perspectives toward the school environment. Phenomenology focuses on the commonality of lived experiences within a group, aiming to describe the essence of a phenomenon (Creswell, 2012). Data collection primarily involves interviews, supported by documents, observations, and other forms of qualitative data. These data are analyzed by identifying significant statements, grouping them into clusters of meaning, and constructing a universal understanding of the experience. Bracketing, or documenting the researcher's personal experiences, is often used to minimize bias and maintain the integrity of the data (Maxwell, 2013). The process culminates in a comprehensive report detailing both the textural (what was experienced) and structural (how it was experienced) aspects of the phenomenon.

Interviews are a central method in phenomenological research, offering in-depth insights into participants' experiences and uncovering the meaning behind their perspectives (Corbetta, 2003). Open-ended questions allow participants to share rich, detailed accounts, while transcription and triangulation ensure accurate and consistent analysis (McNamara, 1999; Quad, 2016). Challenges include the need for researchers to deeply understand phenomenological principles, select participants who have genuinely experienced the phenomenon, and manage the integration of their personal observations into the study. Despite these challenges, phenomenology provides a powerful tool for understanding subjective experiences, uncovering motivations, and challenging assumptions, making it particularly suited for investigating teachers' feelings and experiences within their school environments.

➤ *Research Participants*

The study participants will include seven teachers from the Malita North District, Division of Davao Occidental, selected through purposive sampling based on specific criteria: at least five years of teaching experience, a very satisfactory rating in the new normal IPCRF, and experience

teaching TLE classes. Purposive sampling, also known as judgmental or selective sampling, was chosen to ensure participants align with the study's purpose, enhancing the authenticity of the findings (Creswell, 2014; Marshall, 1996).

➤ *Research Instrument*

The purpose of the research interview is to explore the views, experiences, beliefs and/or motivations of individuals on specific matters. Qualitative methods, such as interviews, are believed to provide a deeper understanding of social phenomena than would be obtained from purely quantitative methods, such as interview questionnaires (Stewart et. al., 2008).

➤ *Data Analysis*

This study employs thematic analysis to examine the data collected from participant interviews, using Creswell's Model for identifying themes. Themes, defined as aggregated codes that represent major ideas, are identified through a systematic process of familiarization, coding, and thematic organization (Creswell, 2012). The researcher immerses herself in the data, generating codes that capture both semantic and conceptual meanings, and organizes these into coherent themes relevant to the research question. Themes are then reviewed for consistency and meaning, with Thematic Content Analysis employed to describe and refine each theme (Andersen, 2013). To enhance validity, Environmental Triangulation is used to assess how varying environmental factors, such as time and location, influence the findings, ensuring consistent results across settings (David, 2015; Naeem & Saira, 2019). The final step involves weaving the themes into an analytic narrative that contextualizes the findings within existing literature.

➤ *Analytical Framework*

The framework analysis for this research offers flexibility, allowing data analysis either after all data is collected or during the collection process. The process involves five stages: familiarization, identifying a thematic framework, indexing, charting, and mapping and interpretation (Ritchie & Spencer, 1994). Familiarization immerses the researcher in the data, enabling recognition of key ideas and recurrent themes. Next, a thematic framework is developed from emerging themes or issues identified during familiarization. Indexing involves marking portions of the data that correspond to specific themes, often using qualitative data analysis tools for organization. Charting organizes the indexed data into thematic charts, and mapping and interpretation analyze the key characteristics, producing a schematic representation of the phenomenon. This final stage helps define concepts, map phenomena, and provide explanations or strategies reflective of participants' authentic attitudes, beliefs, and values (Ritchie & Spencer, 1994).

Fig 2 Analytical Framework of the Study

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Experiences of TLE Teachers as they Conduct Performance-Based Assessment in Distance Learning*

In the new normal of distance learning, performance tasks provide students with engaging, practical activities at home while maintaining a focus on essential learning. According to Adamson (2010), these tasks allow teachers to assess not only what students know but also how they apply that knowledge to new situations or solve problems. TLE teachers, through varied experiences, shift from traditional testing to measuring real-world application and fostering opportunities for students to learn throughout the process.

Acquiring Pedagogical Knowledge and Skills on Distance Learning. Adapting to the new normal has been challenging, particularly for TLE teachers who had to adjust their assessment methods. To ensure education continues during crises, distance learning was implemented, defined by DepEd as a modality where teaching occurs remotely. Transitioning from traditional face-to-face classrooms, TLE teachers require extensive training to effectively navigate distance learning. Participants noted:

“From face-to-face, we are now doing everything online. This is a new normal for us and we teachers need to attend webinars on how to adapt to this new classroom setup.” (P1).

“Learning how to perform distance learning is intensified in times of the pandemic.” (P2)

“Different learning modalities are used in distance learning to continue the teaching-learning process. It also means that we teachers should assess students’ learnings in different modalities. Gladly, there are webinars for teachers to enhance and develop teachers regarding the new setup of assessing students. As a teacher, I need to attend to those webinars in order to update myself to this latest trend.” (P4)

“We teachers are encouraged to attend virtual trainings and workshops in the different learning areas with different modalities in distance learning. I believe this has a good impact to our professional development since we won’t only master the art of teaching in face-to-face class but also in distance learning.” (P5)

Ashraf (2020) emphasized the necessity of training teachers for distance learning, as it demands multitasking—delivering learning materials while assessing how much students have learned. Dillon (2020) supported this, highlighting the challenges of individual assessment and the intense involvement required. Successfully transferring knowledge through virtual education is a vital skill for TLE teachers, making professional training or seminars essential. One participant shared:

“We should take all the opportunities DepEd is providing for us. The webinars conducted regarding distance learning are a big help to us teachers. There are a lot of things to do in this new platform of learning that’s why we teachers should not waste the learnings the department wants to give us.” (P3)

Training and support for distance educators are critical for effective distance learning. Moskal (2020) noted that many teachers are confident in their ability to deliver quality instruction. However, when required to adopt new techniques that limit direct interaction with students and involve unfamiliar pedagogies, they often fear that their teaching quality and evaluations may decline.

Involving Students in the Making. Collaborating with students to create performance tasks is an effective method for fostering the application of their learning. Collins (1982) emphasized that teachers play a crucial role in guiding students to identify key concepts they need to develop, while students contribute by discussing and selecting the aspects of understanding to be assessed. Participants highlighted that:

“Teachers need to involve students in making the performance task, especially rubrics. During performance tasks, I observed that their anxiety is less because they know how the teacher will grade them. They also participate on what components to put in the rubrics that’s why they are more assured of their performance.” (P2)

“In making performance tasks, I ask the students what part of the lesson they are most interested in. I usually base the performance task on the interests of the students.” (P3)

TLE teacher participants believe that involving students in the assessment process enhances learning and motivation, as active participation fosters better engagement. Irabagiza (2007), a counselor at Martyrs School in Rwanda, emphasized that including students in decision-making, particularly on issues that directly affect them, significantly improves academic performance. Since students have firsthand experience with their challenges, allowing them to contribute to class decisions can help TLE teachers address problems more effectively.

“Both teachers and students want to determine what to know and what might be learned next time, so deciding performance tasks should be in collaborative process between teachers and students.” (P3)

“I observe that students are more motivated to accomplish the task if their interests are consulted. I can see improvements in their academic performance.” (P5)

Moreover, aside from involving students in establishing successful criteria and topics, participants also noted that they give students the freedom to choose a way to demonstrate their learning. Participants noted that:

“We have a performance task in which students can choose if they want to demonstrate their understanding

through vlogs, poster, song, etc. I also encourage my students to reflect on the choice they make. How does this choice contribute to your learning progress? What aspect of your work is the most/least effective?” (P4)

“I also consult them if they want to work individually, in pair, or in big groups.” (P6)

Hankov (2018) noted that empowering students to take charge of their learning by making choices and reflecting on their progress fosters engagement and autonomy. Hanover Research (2018) supported this, highlighting that student choice enhances engagement, well-being, and academic performance. When students are involved in their learning, they feel valued, respected, and develop a sense of belonging, attending closely to their educational journey because it reflects their personal experiences. Beyond assessments, TLE teachers also involve students in designing their virtual TLE classrooms, as shared by a participant.

“I enjoy designing virtual classroom with my students. Involving them in creating our class FB group page is such a fun. I encouraged them to put up their ideas, presentations, survey results, and pictures of projects to fill our virtual classroom with learning outcomes. No doubt this generation is into online platforms. By using this platform I can boost the interest and engagement of my students tremendously.” (P7)

Social media and technology have become integral to daily life, with their biggest advantage being enhanced communication. In education, especially during the pandemic, social media has proven invaluable. Students can connect and share learning experiences anytime using smartphones, tablets, or computers, making these platforms essential tools for modern learning (Willbold, 2019).

Extending Time for At-Risk-Students. TLE teacher participants highlighted the increased risk of students facing challenges in distance learning, such as medical issues, learning disabilities, economic hardships, and social anxiety. To address this, they intensify monitoring efforts through phone calls, online messages, and video calls to check on students’ progress with performance tasks and prevent poor academic performance that could lead to dropouts. Unlike face-to-face classes, where teachers can physically observe and address students’ conditions, distance learning limits such direct interaction, making proactive monitoring essential. Participants further shared:

“In reality, not all students can perform the tasks especially tasks that requires gadgets and internet connection. As a teacher, I give them performance tasks tailored to the current situation they are in. This is very important so that this kind of learners can accomplish and submit. Thus, dropping out from school would be avoided.” (P4)

“I think knowing our students will really help us understand why they are performing in class that way. It is indeed difficult to know our students without face to face interaction because with it we can analyze not just their situation but also their bodily action. This is quite impossible

in distance learning. But as teachers I scheduled a talk to them to know them better and of course this will help in designing performance tasks.” (P5)

Participants shared their adjustments in conducting assessments through performance tasks, often comparing face-to-face interactions with the new normal. In face-to-face settings, students are more open to sharing their concerns with teachers due to the trust built through physical interactions, allowing teachers to provide immediate support. However, this dynamic is challenging in distance learning. TLE teachers noted that communication with students online can sometimes feel unresponsive or disconnected. One participant described the online experience as akin to "talking to a brick wall," emphasizing the difficulty in fostering engagement remotely.

“Students felt shy to communicate to their teachers. They seldom talk. I don’t know how they are doing or what their difficulties are.” (P2)

But there are cases in which the parents and the students cannot be contacted, and the TLE teachers shared their experience in taking risks just to visit them. They felt nervous about their safety as well. As they mentioned:

“If I cannot contact these at-risk students, I do some home visitation. I know it is a risk to my health, I’m nervous actually because we don’t know what might happen, but I tried to be really careful and follow health protocols.” (P7)

The importance of parental interaction was mentioned by several TLE teacher participants. They described the experience of obtaining this information as pulling teeth, requiring them to plead for contact information from those who knew the parents of the at-risk students.

“I surveyed my students at the beginning of the year and asked for parent contact information but acknowledged that students may sometimes give an incorrect cellphone number or perhaps their parents change number without informing me.” (P4)

In the absence of face-to-face interactions, TLE teachers often rely on email, phone calls, and texts to effectively communicate with students about their learning tasks. However, these modalities are not commonly used between TLE teachers and students in traditional learning environments; hence both are adjusting to it.

“I think the students felt awkward when I ask them to contact me if they have concerns in doing their performance tasks.” (P1)

“In new normal, establishing communication is very important.” (P4)

“We teachers have to really know our students in order for us to help them on what they need the most.” (P6)

This crisis has highlighted that quality education goes beyond technical infrastructure, platforms, and content; it also requires TLE teachers' dedication to fostering strong relationships with students, delivering lessons remotely, and managing the challenges posed by the pandemic. At the same time, education systems must ensure safe school reopening, minimize dropout rates, and begin recovering lost learning. To ensure a high-quality distance learning experience, education systems must provide teachers with the technological and pedagogical support needed to navigate the short term and build resilience in adapting to the new normal (Wilichowski & Cobo, 2020).

Fig 3 Experience of TLE Teachers as they Conduct Performance-Based Assessment in Distance Learning

The figure illustrates TLE teachers' experiences with performance-based assessments in distance learning, highlighting three key themes: enhancing pedagogical skills for distance learning, involving students in the process, and dedicating extra time to support at-risk students. These experiences reflect teachers' commitment to delivering quality education and fostering student engagement in a remote learning environment.

➤ *Coping Mechanisms of TLE Teachers to the Challenges in Conducting Performance-based Assessment in Distance Learning*

Sotile (2010) emphasized that while implementation strategies may vary in distance learning, the fundamental pedagogical principles behind assessments should remain consistent when transitioning from face-to-face to online courses. Regardless of the mode, assessments must align with course objectives and reliably measure student learning. However, assessing student learning in distance learning presents unique challenges and opportunities, which are discussed below.

Adjusting to Students' Socio Economic Status. Vistor (2020) described the digital divide as inequalities in access to technology and the resources or skills necessary for effective digital learning. Technology has significantly influenced education, transforming teaching methods and content delivery, especially with the shift to distance learning during the pandemic. While it has become essential for students of all levels, disparities in internet and gadget access between affluent and underprivileged, as well as urban and rural students, have led to significant gaps in educational outcomes (Pena, 2020). Participants shared:

"My biggest difficulty is giving performance tasks that needs internet connection and gadgets. Not all students have access to internet and gadgets that's why not all of them can submit the output." (P2)

"One of the challenges I encounter online is that not all students can access the learning materials I gave that could assist them in accomplishing the task." (P3)

"Not all students can respond to the instructional delivery because not all of my students have an access to internet connection. Some of them do not even have gadgets like cell phones, tablets, and computers. Only those who have internet connections and gadgets are updated in the announcements posted in class GC. Students who don't have access to internet can only be updated if their parents go to school to claim the modules and retrieve the answer sheets of their student." (P4)

Wenglinsky (2018) linked effective technology use by students to improved academic performance, but access to technology and academic success often depend on families' socio-economic status (Stanton-Salazar, 1997). Galuszka (2007) noted that despite the widespread availability of technologies like broadband, companies often bypass disadvantaged neighborhoods and schools. To address this, policymakers must ensure equitable distribution of

technological resources so that urban, suburban, and rural schools have equal opportunities to integrate educational technologies. One participant shared:

"Challenges like lack of technology skills, limited or no source of internet connection, lack of gadgets for students were just some of the problems I encountered. Since, we belong to a rural community where most of the students do not have the easy accessibility of internet connection. I ensure that I provide the needed resources or materials that could help students in doing their performance tasks. I made them readily available by printing out the learning resources. In this way, those who do not have gadget and internet connection will still have the change to receive the same learning material to those who have." (P2)

E-learning has significantly transformed traditional education, prompting TLE teachers to address the challenges of the digital divide by providing hard-copy learning materials and instructions. They also accept students' performance tasks in hard-copy format. One participant shared:

"I tailor the performance tasks based on the resources and socio-economic background of my students. In reality, not all students can submit outputs of performance tasks online, that's why I allow those students who do not have access to internet and gadget to show their application of the lesson by posters, essays, etc. rather than requiring them to send videos, pictures, and do vlogs." (P3)

The role of TLE teachers is vital in bridging the digital divide, as they prepare performance task instructions for both students with and without internet access or gadgets. While this adds to their workload, their dedication helps mitigate the digital divide's impact in TLE classes and aligns with the goal of ensuring that no child is left behind.

"I always ensure that I provide the needed resources and instructions to students who do not have internet and gadgets at home. I gave print outs and require them to submit hard copies of the outputs rather than soft copies. In this way, I can assess the learning of this kind of students." (P5)

"One of the challenges that I encounter is that not all students can submit videos, pictures and attend to online class. As a teacher, I give them performance tasks that fits to their budget. If I mandatorily require all my students to submit performance tasks online, those students who do not have internet and gadgets would be depressed and it will negatively impact their academic performance." (P6)

Teachers have strived to address educational challenges in the new normal by supporting students' needs. Ramlall (2020) emphasized that collaboration between schools and stakeholders is crucial to improving distance learning for students lacking internet access and gadgets. With such support, teachers can better navigate these challenges and perform effectively in the new normal.

Employing Different Methods in Monitoring the Quality of Students' Work. Education systems are navigating an

unprecedented challenge, striving to maintain quality education despite the inability of teachers and students to interact in traditional classroom settings. Participants observed:

“It is really a big challenge to monitor the quality of our students’ work in this distance learning platform. As teachers, we need to think of varied, creative, and appropriate ways on how to monitor and assess the works of our students.” (P4)

“In this time, monitoring our student has changed drastically. Accomplishment and coverage of learning outcomes became issues.” (P5)

To tackle these challenges, TLE teachers utilize online platforms to upload performance tasks and learning materials, providing students with clear instructions while enabling parents to monitor their progress. However, many parents are preoccupied with work, leaving limited time to oversee their children’s learning, while TLE teachers face increased paperwork due to the shift in the education system. To address this, teachers implemented monitoring activities to supervise students’ tasks effectively. Participants shared:

“Whenever I give performance tasks to my students – group or individual, I always make sure to schedule a virtual class in order to pre-check the works of my students.” (P1)

“There are times that teachers and parents are busy and cannot respond immediately to queries. With this, I came up with peer review to maximize students’ engagement.” (P5)

“Whenever I give tasks, I always include rubrics so that students at home will be guided on what quality work is. Prior to this, criteria in the rubric are consulted to the students so it means they already have background on how to make outputs that are in good quality.” (P7)

To ensure quality education, TLE teachers must focus on achieving learning outcomes that boost student engagement. These outcomes should not only be measured through grades but also through students’ ability to apply concepts, which can be monitored by assessing deep learning and problem-solving skills through performance tasks (Miller, 2020). Monitoring the quality of students’ work provides teachers with insights into their learning progress (Schofield, 2010) and creates opportunities to motivate and guide students toward meeting class objectives. This interaction enhances student confidence and satisfaction, pushing them to excel. Juillerat (1995) emphasized that classroom-level engagement is closely linked to student satisfaction, which significantly influences persistence and retention.

Scheduling time for assessment design and feedback. Designing performance tasks that align with distance learning is another challenge TLE teachers face in the new setting. While teachers are accustomed to giving performance tasks in face-to-face teaching, these assessments may not suit the new competencies or the mode of submission required in distance learning. As a result, TLE teachers must revise and find innovative ways to implement performance tasks. Participants

acknowledged the need to allocate time for this adjustment, as they noted:

“My strategies for doing performance tasks before are not applicable now in distance learning so I have to think and search for other performance tasks to give to my students’ activities that can be done at home.” (P3)

“There is a need to revise the performance tasks because there are competencies that are not offered in distance learning so I have to spent and schedule time to do it.” (P6)

The participants also emphasized that when designing tasks, TLE teachers must consider various factors to ensure the tasks are achievable. These include the time required to complete the tasks, the availability of materials and resources, and the skills of the learners. As they put it:

“In distance learning, we should consider the availability and if the tasks are doable. Not all students have access to materials and resources; we have to think of that. Unlike in face to face teachers take effort in providing students the resources needed just for them to learn. But in distance learning we have to depend on what is available in their context.” (P7)

Additionally, TLE teachers faced challenges in allocating weekly hours to grade performance task outputs. They stressed the importance of regularly checking these outputs to ensure that students have mastered the necessary competencies before moving on to the next lesson. Since the curriculum is spiral, some competencies must be acquired for students to fully understand future lessons. This is even more critical in distance learning, where direct contact with the teacher is limited. Teachers must consistently check students’ understanding to prevent anyone from falling behind.

Moreover, with most assessments being online, teachers need to dedicate time to provide timely feedback. For TLE teachers, this feedback is crucial for correcting mistakes and motivating students, helping them recognize the value of their efforts in completing the tasks.

“Giving feedback in new normal is very different from face to face. In face to face most of the performance tasks are group work and thus the feedback will be given to the group in general hence it can be done in a limited time. However, in new normal where performance tasks are mostly done individually, feedbacking will indeed take plenty of my time.” (P2)

“I take time in giving feedback to learners in their output because I believe it will motivate them to do better in their tasks.” (P6)

The TLE teachers also observed that when student feedback is given immediately after showing proof of learning, the student responds and remembers the experience about what is being learned more positively and they observe

that the said student will be encourage to comply to other tasks.

“I observe that when they receive feedback they are inspired to do other tasks.” (P5)

“If we wait too long to give feedback, the student might not connect the feedback with the learning moment.” (P6)

Feedback plays a crucial role in enhancing learning by helping students understand the subject matter and offering clear guidance for improvement. Bellon et al. (1991) emphasize that academic feedback is more strongly linked to achievement than any other teaching behavior, and this holds true across various student demographics. Feedback boosts student confidence, self-awareness, and enthusiasm for learning.

Studies show that students respond better to assessments when they receive plenty of practice with the same types of

tasks, accompanied by both written and oral feedback. This approach helps students gradually understand the goals and standards expected of them, which is a key component of effective assessment design. Incorrect assessment timing or sequencing can hinder learning opportunities (TESTA, 2019).

Rovai (2000) highlights that while the principles of assessment remain the same in online environments, their application differs. He recommends proctored testing and online discussions for distance courses. Proctored testing, including methods like delayed phone calls, online chats, or email, helps ensure identity security and academic integrity, especially in high-stakes assessments.

Robles and Braathen (2002) suggest that traditional assessment techniques can be adapted for distance learning, proposing tools such as self-tests, assignments, electronic portfolios, online discussions, and synchronous chats. These methods can effectively determine whether students have achieved the desired learning objectives in an online setting.

Fig 4 Coping Mechanism of TLE Teachers of the Challenges in Conducting Performance-Based Assessment in Distance Learning

The figure above illustrates how TLE teachers cope with the challenges of conducting performance-based assessments in distance learning. Three key themes emerged from the participants' responses: adjusting to students' socio-economic status, using various methods to monitor the quality of students' work, and managing time for assessment design and feedback. Their responses clearly highlight that TLE teachers' coping mechanisms are student-centered.

Effective distance learning does not occur automatically but requires careful and intentional design, as noted by Dougherty & Schantz (2020). It involves empowering students to take charge of their learning. A student-centered

approach is essential for ensuring more meaningful and equitable learning outcomes for all students in distance learning settings.

➤ *Educational Management Insights Drawn from the Experiences of TLE Teachers*

Life Long Learning and Being Open to Change. Distance learning adheres to the use of technology. The participants are continuously familiarizing themselves with different online learning platforms. To equip themselves with the new normal education, the TLE teachers attend webinar sessions, watch video tutorials, and are mentored by peers.

“Continuous development has been the trend even before, but for me, this pandemic has strengthened the need of teachers to learn.” (P1)

“We should attend webinars for us teachers to be updated with the latest trend. We can learn new teaching strategies suitable in distance learning.” (P2)

“In the new normal, learning is a must. I have to learn how to use computers and how to integrate them in class. I am not good with computers but I am trying to learn. Learning must continue especially now.” (P4)

Constant learning widens teachers' knowledge and develops useful skills as they design their instructional plans which include assessment. Constant learning provides growth and development of teachers as professionals, making them ready and prepared in embracing changes in the teaching landscape. Teachers play a significant role in improving the quality of education; hence, capacity building of teachers must receive top priority (Aslam, 2014).

“If this pandemic did not happen, I think we will not fully make use of these online resources. I think this is one of the things we learned from this pandemic.” (P1)

“Before it did not occur to me to use messenger and Facebook in giving instructions for performance tasks, and even use them in submission. Now from attending training and seminars I learned all about these, what was once seems impossible is now possible. We can connect to others even at a distance.” (P3)

“I was amazed by learning new teaching trends especially in conducting performance tasks assessment using YouTube, Zoom, Google Meet and Facebook.” (5)

“Attending training and seminars has a lot of benefit one is that we can add something from our learning bank.” (P6)

Today's teaching careers have drastically changed over the past two decades, with education evolving rapidly, causing techniques, skills, and technologies to become outdated in just a few years. This is why being a lifelong learner is crucial for educators. It helps them incorporate new tools and strategies into the learning process, enhancing student development (EDU, 2018). Lifelong learning is not a luxury but a necessity, essential for shaping the future of societies (Fischer, 2018).

Teachers who embrace lifelong learning are more successful in overcoming challenges. They view mistakes as opportunities for growth rather than failures, using them to gather information for solving problems. By adopting a mindset of continuous learning, teachers can adapt to changes and better respond to student needs. This habit of self-education allows them to hone their existing skills, develop new ones, and ease transitions when changes occur (Jun, 2018).

Escalating Students' Engagement. Teachers are advised to invest sufficient time designing appropriate performance tasks for the purpose of encouraging student engagement (Abrami et al., 2011; Banna et al., 2015). TLE Teachers should be critical in choosing material, content, and criteria for grading when they wish to engage students more in the task. Content includes the subject matter knowledge to be learned, as well as everything else about the instruction in which the subject matter knowledge is embedded—including the activity of the instruction and the input of teachers and students in the instruction (Rogoff, 2000). With this, Students should not merely be given a list of resources, but instead teachers should design authentic activities that provide opportunities to examine the tasks from different perspectives and that encourage students to wisely use relevant information in the process (Dixson, 2010).

“As a TLE teacher, I should provide students with real life application of the concepts I am teaching through performance tasks because it would enhance subject mastery, critical thinking skills and communication skills.” (P1)

“I believe that distance learning, if handled properly, can let students engage in the content more and they can have a wide avenue for enhancing their outputs. Let us give them a chance to interact with the learning resources available online and offline to produce better performances.” (P5)

“As a teacher, I get to know all my students even in distance learning class and use that knowledge to create meaningful performance tasks. I examine my students' interest and know their talents and skills.” (P7)

Getting to know students' skills, abilities, and interests provides valuable insights that influence student engagement and readiness. These factors, along with the instructional activities and setting, create stimuli that motivate students (Billmord, 1998). Engagement refers to the cognitive interaction between students and instructional content. It can involve activities such as attending a lecture or discussion, comparing new information with prior knowledge, rehearsing facts, or only partially focusing on the lesson (Boyle, 1993).

“It adds additional knowledge and ideas from the particular topic which is not properly discussed in the module. It is used as reference, thereby increasing students' engagement which results to better outputs in class.” (P6)

“With the help of online learning platforms we can build students' engagement and also their creativity.” (P7)

Student engagement is crucial for learning, as more engagement is linked to greater learning, according to Resnick (1991). He emphasized that engagement is driven by both the student and the instructional content, making it important for content to be authentic and relevant to students' lives. This is because students bring stable characteristics such as physiological needs, motivators, and prior knowledge to the learning process. Effective instructional content should be paired with assessments aligned to the objectives, allowing students to apply what they've learned and demonstrating their

understanding. Blanca (2014) highlighted the importance of aligning expectations, success criteria, instructional content, and assessments to accurately evaluate student knowledge.

Being Sensitive and Responsive. TLE teachers believe that in distance learning, it is essential to be responsive to students' diverse needs, especially given their varying socioeconomic backgrounds. Baker (2014) defined socioeconomic background as a combined measure of a person's work experience, economic access to resources, and social position. Thomson (2011) highlighted the link between lower socioeconomic status and learning disabilities or psychological issues that impact academic achievement. Children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds are twice as likely to face learning-related challenges compared to those from higher-status households. In response, TLE teachers aim to structure inclusive teaching methods that promote multiple modes of engagement, provide various pathways for success, and create an accessible learning environment.

“My students who have internet connection at home prefers to receive their feedbacks online because it is more convenient to them. They also prefer to submit their outputs online because it is also more convenient. On the other hand, there are also students and parents who request printed copies of instructions and request onsite submission of the outputs since they do not have internet at home. I respect their preferences and capability. As their TLE teachers, I don't focus on single method only. I apply wide range of communications to my students because they have varied needs, interests, and preferences. I respect and cater them because they affect students' academic achievement.” (P3)

“I have personalized strategies for improvement for each student. Those students of mine who cannot access the internet usually receive offline or printed intervention materials. I usually monitor their outputs and progress

through phone calls or scheduled face to face meetings with their parents.” (P4)

“Rather than hold online giving of feedbacks which low socioeconomic status students often cannot join, I call them via the cellular phone. Sometimes, I also schedule the parent to see me personally so that I could discuss the learning progress of his/her child.” (P5)

Technology offers new opportunities for communication, allowing teachers to connect with students beyond school hours and locations (Brewer & Kallick, 2000). For example, student performances can be recorded and shared with a larger audience, and digital portfolios of students' work can be regularly shared with parents. Learning plans and progress can also be accessed online, strengthening the link between homes and schools. However, Hayat (2020) emphasized the need to incorporate offline features in distance learning plans, as some students lack internet access.

TLE teachers' responses show their sensitivity and responsiveness to student needs. Madison (2016) highlighted that teachers' awareness of students' needs and interests helps anticipate challenges and provide the right level of support. When teachers are sensitive to students, they offer academic and socioeconomically appropriate opportunities that challenge students at a reasonable level, making them feel supported and reassured. One participant shared:

“I do both online and offline performance tasks in the class. I am aware that not all of my students can do online tasks, that's why I take time designing tasks that are good for offline students too. I don't want them to be left behind because they might dropout from school. I reassure them that distance learning is not only successful for students who have internet and gadgets, but it is also successful for them.” (P4)

Fig 5 Education Management Insights Drawn from the Experience of Teachers

IV. IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

➤ *Implications*

This study offers valuable insights into the experiences of TLE teachers in conducting performance-based assessments in distance learning, with several implications for various stakeholders in education. For DepEd officials, the findings provide guidance on which topics and content should be prioritized in webinars and training programs, particularly in relation to assessment strategies for distance learning. School administrators can gain a deeper understanding of the efforts teachers make to employ varied assessment strategies that accommodate students with different levels of access to the internet and gadgets. By providing technical support, such as assistance in reviewing performance task designs and criteria, administrators can help make assessments more reliable, appropriate, and meaningful for students.

For teachers, the study is significant as it offers an opportunity to share best practices and gain insights into designing and implementing performance task assessments in the new normal. By reflecting on the management insights drawn from their experiences, teachers can further enhance their assessment practices. Stakeholders, including community members and local organizations, can use the study's findings to assist school administrators in delivering effective assessment methods for distance learning. The study also highlights the need for funds to produce offline learning materials, which would help students in completing performance tasks. Lastly, for future researchers, the study provides comprehensive data that can be used in conducting similar or related research, contributing to the broader knowledge of performance-based assessment in distance learning. Ultimately, this study emphasizes the importance of understanding teachers' experiences and adapting assessment strategies to meet the diverse needs of students in the evolving educational landscape.

➤ *Future Directions*

Several areas for future studies in this field warrant further exploration. One recommendation is to investigate the perspectives and experiences of school administrators regarding the supervision of teachers' instructions and assessment methods in the new normal. Examining these aspects would provide valuable educational management insights into how supervision can be effectively conducted in the context of a new normal classroom setup. Such research would contribute to a better understanding of the challenges and best practices in overseeing instructional practices and assessment strategies, ultimately enhancing the overall effectiveness of education in the distance learning environment. These findings could have significant implications for improving the organizational and hierarchical structures within the education sector, ensuring that both teachers and administrators are better equipped to meet the needs of students in an ever-evolving educational landscape.

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